

Software Families Survey Protocol

*Required

1. Kindly first read the informed consent form in the link below. By checking the box you confirm that you have read and agree with the contents in the informed consent form. *

Tick all that apply.

I agree to participate in this survey.

Software Families Survey Protocol

2. Qn.1: Kindly restate the name of your variant we identified in the e-mail to help us link your responses with your variant. *
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3. Qn.2: How many of the original developers of the mainline maintained the variant in its first 6 months? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0, none of the initial maintainers of the variant were originally part of the mainline
- 1, maintainer
- 2 - 5, maintainers
- 6 - 10, maintainers
- >10, maintainers
- I do not remember. It has been a long time since the variant was created

4. Qn.3: Do the variant and mainline have common active maintainers? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, they have common maintainers
- No, they do not have common maintainers
- They used to have common maintainers in the early stages of the variant, but now the projects have technically diverged away from each other, there are no more common maintainers.
- I am not sure since the projects are too and the contributors in the maintenance team are very many

5. Qn.4: What was the motivation of creating the variant of the mainline project? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Not Applicable	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Agree	Strongly Agree
TECHNICAL. The variant was introduced to target specific needs or user segments that are not accommodated by the mainline project	<input type="radio"/>				
GOVERNANCE DISPUTES. The variant was created because some of the contributors felt that their feedback was not heard or maintainers were accepting patches too slowly in the mainline project.	<input type="radio"/>				
LEGAL. The mainline or variant wanted to change its license or change its laws (e.g., regarding encryption) requiring technical changes.	<input type="radio"/>				
PERSONAL. There were interpersonal disputes and irreconcilable differences of a non-technical nature that led to a rift between various parties.	<input type="radio"/>				
OTHERS	<input type="radio"/>				

6. Qn.5: Kindly provide details for your selected answer(s) in Qn.4 above.

For example, If the main reason was Governance disputes, it would be nice to know if there was an attempt to fix the issue before; It would be also nice to know how the mainline and variant have evolved afterwards (e.g. it could be the case that a license issue lead to the fork but then the fork diverged technically), etc.

7. Qn.6: If there are any links that are documented relating to your choice of answers in Qn.4 as well as details in Qn.5, kindly point us there.

8. Qn.7: Was the motivation for creating the variant an individual decision or a community decision? *

Mark only one oval.

Individual decision

Community decision

9. Qn.8: Do the variant and mainline still discuss the main directions of the project, the new features, etc? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes, they still discuss the direction of the projects
- They used to discuss but not anymore since the projects have technically diverged from each other
- No, there has never been any discussion since the creation of the variant
- I do not discuss, but I am not sure if other maintainers do
- Other: _____

10. Qn.9: How often do the maintainers of the variant integrate the following types of changes from the mainline? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
New features	<input type="radio"/>				
Bug Fixes	<input type="radio"/>				
Security fixes	<input type="radio"/>				
Refactoring	<input type="radio"/>				
Documentation	<input type="radio"/>				
Others	<input type="radio"/>				

11. If your answer for "Others" in Qn.9 above was something other than "Never", kindly write what it represents. If you would like to give us details for your choice of answers in Qn.9, kindly state them here.

12. Qn.10: How often do the maintainers of the variant integrate the following types of changes into the mainline? *

Mark only one oval per row.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
New features	<input type="radio"/>				
Bug fixes	<input type="radio"/>				
Security Fixes	<input type="radio"/>				
Refactoring	<input type="radio"/>				
Documentation	<input type="radio"/>				
Others	<input type="radio"/>				

13. If your answer for "Others" in Qn.10 above was something other than "Never", kindly write what it represents. If you would like to give us details for your choice of answers in Qn.10, kindly state them here.

14. If you wish the conclusions to be sent to you or to be contacted for follow-up studies, kindly select one or both of the following checkboxes.

Tick all that apply.

- I wish to be sent the conclusions of the study
- I wish to be contacted for follow-up studies

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